

Environmental implications of economic complexity and its role in determining how renewable energies affect CO₂ emissions

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Economic complexity increases energy efficiency.
- The substitution effects of renewable energy result in decreased CO₂ emissions.
- The scale effects of renewable energy result in increased CO₂ emissions.
- In higher complex economies, the scale effects dominate substitution.
- In lower economic complexity, the substitution effect is more for wind and solar.

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ABSTRACT

The economic complexity index's environmental implications have been thoroughly investigated in this study. In particular, an effort is made to determine the index's utility in explaining and filling in the gaps left by experimental studies on the effects of renewable energy on CO₂ emissions. The study sampled 29 Asia-Pacific countries over the period 2000–2018. The relationship between the complexity index and CO₂ emissions has been investigated using panel data models and estimation methods. According to the findings, increasing the intensity of energy use, trade openness, and urbanization all increase CO₂ emissions, although the effects of urbanization eventually became insignificant in the long run. Furthermore, while the logarithm of GDP per capita's coefficients for the level and squared forms confirmed the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis, the economic complexity index shifted the curve. The results indicate that economic complexity in countries enhances economic growth effects to increase CO₂ emissions through increased production scale and energy demand. On the other hand, increasing economic complexity through increased energy efficiency demonstrates its beneficial effects on the environment. According to the findings, increasing wind and solar energy share has reduced CO₂ emissions in countries with lower economic complexity. In comparison, in more complex countries along with these substitution effects, there is also a scale effect associated with increasing renewable energy use, which eventually results in increased CO₂ emissions.

1. Introduction

Greenhouse gases, including CO₂, methane, and nitrous oxide, are typically produced by industrial activities such as transportation, power plants, and energy-intensive industries. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions account for approximately 75% of greenhouse gas emissions [1], increasing global temperature by 1.5 °C, deemed relatively high. Thus, economic sustainability has become a global priority over the last two

decades, attracting environmental scholars, policymakers, and international organizations in various countries. This phenomenon resulted in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change being established in 1992. Later, in 1997, the Kyoto Protocol and the 2015 Paris Agreement were developed to combat global warming by limiting greenhouse gas emissions [2].

While endogenous economic growth theory emphasizes the importance of research and development (R&D) investments in improving

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resource efficiency [3], empirical research on such effects has produced no consensus. According to some researchers, technological innovations can help reduce CO₂ emissions and improve environmental quality [4–8]. There are numerous reasons for technology's negative impact on CO₂ emissions. For instance, tightening environmental regulations fosters a continuous increase in environmental innovations to lower CO₂ emissions [9]. By altering the traditional economic development process based on production factors, an innovation-based model can reduce CO₂ emissions associated with industrialization through increased energy efficiency [10]. Additionally, several studies have discovered that technological innovations may adversely or insignificantly affect the environment's quality [11–14]. The studies indicate that while modern technologies can increase resource efficiency, resulted in the rapidly expanding economic scale which imposes the necessity for additional investments in maintaining the quality of natural resources [12].

Furthermore, experimental studies have yielded no conclusive evidence regarding the effect of renewable energy consumption on greenhouse gas emissions. Several experimental studies concluded that consuming renewable energy had a net effect of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. According to Bilgili et al. [15], renewable energy consumption aided in reducing carbon emissions in 17 OECD countries. Moreover, their findings refute the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) hypothesis. Moutinho and Robaina [16] provide compelling evidence for the validity of the EKC and demonstrate how renewable energy development can contribute significantly to CO₂ emission reductions. According to Zoundi [17], renewable energy helped African countries reduce their CO₂ emissions. Kahia et al. [18] demonstrated that renewable energy increased economic growth and decreased CO₂ emissions in MENA countries. Hu et al. [19] examined the role of renewable energy in 25 developing countries' CO₂ emissions. Their findings indicated that the use of renewable energy decreased CO₂ emissions. Chen et al. [20] obtained comparable results and reported that renewable energy significantly reduced carbon emissions. Bekun et al. [21] discovered that CO₂ emissions decreased in 16 European Union countries due to renewable energy consumption.

Besides, numerous studies emphasize the insignificant or even enhancing effects of renewable energy consumption on the spread of greenhouse gas emissions, resulting in findings that vary by country. Apergis and Payne [22] demonstrated that renewable energy did not contribute to short-term emissions reductions in the 19 advanced and developing countries studied. Farhani [23] reported a one-way causal relationship between CO₂ emissions and renewable energy consumption in the short term but did not analyze the direction of causality between CO₂ emissions and renewable energy consumption as a whole. Jebli et al. [24] found no direct causal relationship between carbon dioxide emissions and renewable energy consumption. Jebli and Youssef's [25] study of five North African countries demonstrated that renewable energy consumption increased CO₂ emissions. Da Silva et al. [26] found that one of the barriers to renewable energy consumption in the 17 Sub-Saharan (SSA) countries studied was CO₂ emissions. Nguyen and Kakinaka [27] reported that renewable energy consumption increased greenhouse gas emissions in low-income countries. Saidi and Omri [28] recently observed that investments in renewable energy had resulted in CO₂ emissions reductions in Belgium, Sweden, Canada, the Czech Republic, Germany, the United Kingdom, France, the United States, Japan, Finland, and Finland Switzerland. However, in the Netherlands and South Korea, the findings reported an increase in CO₂ emissions.

Such disparate findings in the experimental literature regarding the effects of renewable energy and technological innovation on CO₂ emissions highlight the hidden dimensions of a country's economic structure, influencing the findings depending on the sample of countries

studied. Given that green investment is defined as investing in renewable technologies, selecting energy-efficient technologies, and conducting research and development on green technologies [29], renewable energy and R&D are inextricably linked and can have varying spillover effects on one another [30,31]. However, the economic structure serves as the foundation for determining the level of research and development in green technologies and how to expand renewable energy sources.

According to classical development theories, economic progress is associated with structural changes and advances in knowledge and technology, plus the resulting diversity of products and services and economic complexity [32,33]. Thus, the process of acquiring the ability to produce and export more complex products may be a logical explanation for the economic development process [34,35]. On the other hand, economic complexity enables the spread of effective products such as renewable energies within a country. Knowledge management in large production networks produces various primary knowledge-insensitive products [36]. Economic complexity indicates a greater capacity for producing and exporting more complex, higher-value-added products. It explains why developed countries have comparative advantages in producing goods while requiring increased coordination in highly skilled human capital [37].

The economic complexity of countries has been overlooked in experimental studies; therefore, this study's primary objective is to examine the role of economic complexity in renewable energy development and its subsequent effect on CO₂ emissions. This issue becomes more prominent as new research highlights the environmental role of economic complexity as one of the structural differences between countries' economies. Can and Gozgor [38] proposed that increasing economic complexity reduces overall CO₂ emissions. Neagu and Teodoru [39] indicated that countries with higher economic complexity of products experience a faster decline in CO₂ emissions due to differences in energy composition and energy efficiency. However, increased economic complexity may result in further environmental degradation due to increased production and demand for energy. Neagu [36] recently reported that economic complexity during the initial stages of exports contributed to pollution (due to the widespread use of resources to maintain export products). After a certain point, economic complexity results in reduced pollution through less polluting resources and technologies.

Several new contributions have been proposed in this study: 1) Given that a country's economic structure reflects its degree of development, it is critical to determine the complexity and quality of goods produced in an economy. Such a composition in manufactured products can reveal different environmental effects. Thus, this research examined the scale and efficiency effects of the economic complexity index on CO₂ emissions using a widely cited indicator of economic transformation known as the Economic Complexity Index (ECI), developed by Harvard University. The index's effect on the changed energy efficiency and displacement of the EKC has been investigated for this purpose. 2) For bridging the gaps in the experimental literature and reach a consensus on the effect of renewable energy on CO₂ emissions, the implications of countries' economic structures on such an effect have been examined. The role of economic complexity in explaining the contradictory effects of renewable energy on emissions has been investigated. Consequently, the role of economic complexity in developing various forms of renewable energy (including hydropower, wind, solar, geothermal, and bioenergy energy resources) and its spillover effects on how renewable energy affects CO₂ emissions have been extensively studied.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: The second section contains data and models describing the factors influencing CO₂

emissions. The third section analyzes the findings, and the fourth section concludes with a conclusion and discusses the study's policy implications.

2. Model and data description

The study examines the determinants of CO2 emissions in 29 Asia-Pacific countries using annual data from 2000 to 2018¹. CO2 emissions per capita in these countries are depicted in Fig. 1. Following the empirical findings, a set of potential CO2 emission-related factors is verified. CO2 emissions are modeled as a function of the logarithm of GDP per capita ($\ln GDP$), GDP per capita in squared form ($\ln GDP^2$), renewable energy production ($\ln RENEW$), urbanization ($\ln URB$), trade openness ($\ln OPE$), energy intensity ($\ln ENER$), and the Economic Complexity Index (ECI).

$$\ln CO_{2it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln GDP_{it}^2 + \beta_4 \ln URB_{it} + \beta_5 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_6 \ln ENER_{it} + \beta_7 \ln RENEW_{it} + \beta_8 ECI_{it} \quad (1)$$

where \ln denotes the variables' logarithmic transformation, the estimated coefficients are elasticities. Economic growth and environmental quality are related, as demonstrated by the EKC hypothesis. According to this hypothesis, the environment's quality is an inverted U-shape, which correlates with economic development. As economic growth accelerates, the quality of the environment degrades initially before improving. As a result, the GDP per capita squared form coefficient in the CO2 emissions equation must be negative [40]. Increased economic activity and GDP result in increased energy consumption and, as a result, CO2 emissions. However, scale effects lead to a rise in demand for a healthier environment, resulting in tightened regulations. The term "income-induced technique effects" refers to these effects [41]. Additionally, variables related to urbanization and energy use [42–44] as well as trade openness [45,46] are frequently used as explanatory variables for CO2 emissions. Economic growth and environmental quality are related, as demonstrated by the EKC hypothesis.

Furthermore, the following Equation is estimated to determine the spillover effects of the economic complexity index on energy efficiency and the development pattern of the EKC for countries with varying degrees of economic complexity:

$$\ln CO_{2it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln GDP_{it}^2 + \beta_4 \ln URB_{it} + \beta_5 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_6 \ln ENER_{it} + \beta_7 \ln RENEW_{it} + \beta_8 (ECI_{it} \times \ln ENER_{it}) + \beta_9 (ECI_{it} \times \ln GDP_{it}) + \beta_{10} (ECI_{it} \times \ln GDP_{it}^2) \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), the effect of energy intensity on carbon emissions is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{d(\ln CO_{2it})}{d(\ln ENER_{it})} = \beta_6 + \beta_8 ECI_{it}$$

At a negative β_8 in Eq. (2), a more complex economy would mitigate the effects of energy intensity on CO2 emissions and vice versa, implying that the Economic Complexity Index has a beneficial effect on energy efficiency. Moreover, the EKC derived from Eq. (2) is as follows, which, as can be seen, alters the slope of the EKC when the economic complexity

¹ Including Vietnam, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Thailand, Tajikistan, Sri Lanka, Singapore, Russian Federation, Philippines, Pakistan, New Zealand, Myanmar, Mongolia, Malaysia, Kyrgyz Republic, Kazakhstan, Japan, Iran, Indonesia, India, Georgia, China, Cambodia, Bangladesh, Azerbaijan, Australia, Armenia, and South Korea

Fig. 1. CO2 Emissions per capita in the sampled countries.

index coefficients are significant:

$$CO_{2it} = (\beta_2 + \beta_9 ECI_{it}) \times \ln GDP_{it} + (\beta_3 + \beta_{10} ECI_{it}) \times \ln GDP_{it}^2 \quad (3)$$

Additionally, to examine the spillover effects of the economic complexity index on the effectiveness of renewable energy in reducing CO2 emissions, the following Equation was estimated:

$$\ln CO_{2it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln GDP_{it}^2 + \beta_4 \ln URB_{it} + \beta_5 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_6 \ln ENER_{it} + \beta_7 \ln RENEW_{it} + \beta_8 (ECI_{it} \times \ln RENEW_{it}) \quad (4)$$

Also, the coefficient of the interaction term of ($ECI_{it} \times \ln RENEW_{it}$) demonstrates the interaction between the economic complexity index and renewable energy production. The derivate of Eq. (2) concerning

$\ln RENEW_{it}$ is calculated as follows to investigate the marginal effects of renewable energy resources on CO2 emissions:

$$\frac{d(\ln CO_{2it})}{d(\ln RENEW_{it})} = \beta_7 + \beta_8 ECI_{it}$$

Given that the value of some of the independent variables is less than one or equal to zero in some years, the value of the independent variable is added to one before its logarithmic transformation and inclusion in models. The variables constructed and the data sources are listed in Table 1.

Table 2 summarizes the data from 1996 to 2018. The standard deviations are smaller than the means for most variables, indicating the absence of outliers and a low level of variation in the model's variables over a relatively long period.

3. Presentation and results analysis

The effects of CO2 emission determinants have been investigated in this study using various diagnostic tests and econometric models of data

Table 1
Definitions of variables.

Variable	Variable constructed	Source
$\ln CO_{2it}$	$\ln CO_{2it} = \log(CO_{2it})$ CO_{2it} = CO ₂ Emissions (metric tons per capita)	IEA
$\ln GDPP_{it}$	$\ln GDPP_{it} = \log(GDPP_{it})$ $GDPP_{it}$ = GDP per capita (constant 2010 US\$)	WDI
$\ln URB_{it}$	$\ln URB_{it} = \log(URB_{it})$ URB_{it} = Urban population (% of the total population)	WDI
$\ln OPE_{it}$	$\ln OPE_{it} = \log(OPE_{it})$ OPE_{it} = Trade Openness (% of GDP)	WDI
$\ln ENER_{it}$	$\ln ENER_{it} = \log(ENER_{it})$ $ENER_{it}$ = Energy intensity (energy use as a percentage of GDP)	IEA
$\ln RENEW_{it}$	$\ln RENEW_{it} = \log(1 + RENEW_{it})$ $RENEW_{it}$ = Renewable Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln HYD_{it}$	$\ln HYD_{it} = \log(1 + HYD_{it})$ HYD_{it} = Hydropower Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln SOL_{it}$	$\ln SOL_{it} = \log(1 + SOL_{it})$ SOL_{it} = Solar Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln WIN_{it}$	$\ln WIN_{it} = \log(1 + WIN_{it})$ WIN_{it} = Wind Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln BIO_{it}$	$\ln BIO_{it} = \log(1 + BIO_{it})$ BIO_{it} = Bioenergy Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln GEO_{it}$	$\ln GEO_{it} = \log(1 + GEO_{it})$ GEO_{it} = Geothermal Energy per capita	SDG
ECl_{it}	ECl_{it} = Economic Complexity Index	Harvard's Growth Lab

WDI: World Development Indicator; <https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/dataset/world-development-indicators>.

IEA: International Energy Agency; <https://webstore.iea.org/>.

Harvard's Growth Lab; <https://atlas.cid.harvard.edu/rankings>.

SDG: The Asia-Pacific SDG Gateway; <https://data.unescap.org/>.

panels. Along with estimating relationships using conventional panel models with fixed and random effects, long-term effects of variables are estimated for this purpose. Fig. 2 illustrates the calculation method used in this study. The flowchart depicts the process of developing a panel regression model.

3.1. Unit root tests

The stationarity test results in Table 3 (including Levin, Lin, & Chu [47]; Im, Pesaran, & Shin [48]; ADF-Fisher; & PP-Fisher) demonstrate that the majority of variables are integrated of the order I (1) at a 1% significance level.

3.2. Estimation results

Given that the model's variables are integrated to the order of one, the long-run effects of the model's variables on CO2 emissions are estimated using Phillips and Moon's [49] panel cointegrating estimators for the panel fully modified OLS (PFMOLS) model. Due to the cointegration relationship, using the traditional pooled least squares method

may result in biased estimates. By applying a non-parametric transformation to the residuals obtained from the cointegration regression, the panel FMOLS estimator generates consistent estimates of the parameters in relatively small samples and accounts for the regressors' possible endogeneity and serial correlation. The relative stability of the output of different models' estimation results demonstrates the estimated coefficients' accuracy.

All models are specified as functions of key variables such as GDP per capita, urbanization, trade openness, and energy intensity. Additionally, each model's nested model is specified in terms of the gradual inclusion of the economic complexity index, renewable energies, and interaction terms. Model 1 presents the estimated values for Eq. (1), models 2 and 3 present the estimated values for Eq. (2), and models 4 to 15 present the estimated values for Eq. (4). It is worth noting that models 4–9 do not include the interaction term in Eq. (4) for the various components of renewable energy, whereas models 10–15 include this term. Two distinct likelihood ratio (LR) tests are used to compare the 15 estimated models. The probability of time-period and spatial fixed effects was examined in the conventional panel model, and the results are summarized in Table 4. Models with simultaneous fixed effects of time-

Table 2
Statistics summary (2000–2018).

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Observations
$\ln CO_{2it}$	0.921	1.152	2.907	-1.938	1.257	551
$\ln GDPP_{it}$	8.297	8.161	10.987	5.835	1.327	551
$\ln URB_{it}$	3.886	3.947	4.605	2.901	0.454	551
$\ln OPE_{it}$	4.158	4.154	6.081	-1.787	0.951	551
$\ln ENER_{it}$	1.774	1.724	3.554	0.625	0.490	551
$\ln RENEW_{it}$	1.765	1.218	5.956	0.012	1.718	551
$\ln HYD_{it}$	1.598	1.033	5.859	0.000	1.734	551
$\ln SOL_{it}$	0.127	0.001	2.950	0.000	0.388	551
$\ln WIN_{it}$	0.207	0.000	3.542	0.000	0.630	551
$\ln BIO_{it}$	0.228	0.004	2.344	0.000	0.535	551
$\ln GEO_{it}$	0.133	0.000	3.838	0.000	0.642	551
ECl_{it}	0.017	-0.100	2.895	-1.609	0.939	551

Fig. 2. The calculation procedure used to construct a panel regression model.

Table 3
The panel unit root tests.

Variable	Method	Level		First Difference	
		Statistic	p-value	Statistic	p-value
$\ln CO_{2it}$	Levin, Lin, and Chu	-2.933	(0.002 ^{***})	-7.572	(0.000 ^{***})
	Im, Pesaran, and Shin	1.802	(0.964)	-7.753	(0.000 ^{***})
	ADF-Fisher	50.185	(0.758)	167.572	(0.000 ^{***})
	PP-Fisher	52.061	(0.695)	313.801	(0.000 ^{***})
$\ln GDPP_{it}$	Levin, Lin, and Chu	-4.037	(0.000 ^{***})	-6.279	(0.000 ^{***})
	Im, Pesaran, and Shin	1.537	(0.938)	-5.900	(0.000 ^{***})
	ADF-Fisher	55.065	(0.585)	133.096	(0.000 ^{***})
	PP-Fisher	357.539	(0.000 ^{***})	205.942	(0.000 ^{***})
$\ln URB_{it}$	Levin, Lin, and Chu	-11.689	(0.000 ^{***})	1.879	(0.970)
	Im, Pesaran, and Shin	-4.337	(0.000 ^{***})	1.672	(0.953)
	ADF-Fisher	394.551	(0.000 ^{***})	279.913	(0.000 ^{***})
	PP-Fisher	1149.650	(0.000 ^{***})	221.261	(0.000 ^{***})
$\ln OPE_{it}$	Levin, Lin, and Chu	-2.867	(0.002 ^{***})	-7.420	(0.000 ^{***})
	Im, Pesaran, and Shin	-0.981	(0.163)	-8.491	(0.000 ^{***})
	ADF-Fisher	63.890	(0.277)	183.014	(0.000 ^{***})
	PP-Fisher	60.804	(0.375)	319.807	(0.000 ^{***})
$\ln ENER_{it}$	Levin, Lin, and Chu	-1.541	(0.062 [*])	-7.221	(0.000 ^{***})
	Im, Pesaran, and Shin	1.896	(0.971)	-7.351	(0.000 ^{***})
	ADF-Fisher	51.577	(0.711)	162.461	(0.000 ^{***})
	PP-Fisher	71.350	(0.112)	281.955	(0.000 ^{***})
$\ln RENEW_{it}$	Levin, Lin, and Chu	-1.572	(0.058 [*])	-6.906	(0.000 ^{***})
	Im, Pesaran, and Shin	6.434	(1.000)	-4.160	(0.000 ^{***})
	ADF-Fisher	36.433	(0.988)	118.723	(0.000 ^{***})
	PP-Fisher	29.388	(0.999)	317.446	(0.000 ^{***})

Note: p-values in parentheses, ^{***}, ^{**}, and ^{*} show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 4
The likelihood ratio (LR) test.

Model	Spatial fixed effects		Time-period fixed effects	
	Statistic	p-value	Statistic	p-value
Model A1	33.459	(0.021 ^{**})	1307.887	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A2	35.015	(0.014 ^{**})	1312.761	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A3	27.320	(0.097 [*])	1358.845	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A4	34.071	(0.018 ^{**})	1209.908	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A5	38.654	(0.005 ^{***})	1308.876	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A6	44.985	(0.001 ^{***})	1309.815	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A7	35.671	(0.012 ^{**})	1305.359	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A8	45.347	(0.001 ^{***})	1271.226	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A9	32.717	(0.026 ^{**})	1202.868	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A10	33.594	(0.021 ^{**})	1185.223	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A11	30.063	(0.051 [*])	1321.779	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A12	40.138	(0.003 ^{***})	1248.573	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A13	35.540	(0.012 ^{**})	1300.147	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A14	44.634	(0.001 ^{***})	1276.518	(0.000 ^{***})
Model A15	30.062	(0.051 [*])	1163.428	(0.000 ^{***})

Note: p-values in parentheses, ^{***}, ^{**}, and ^{*} show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively. Source: Authors' estimations.

period and spatial were compared to the separated fixed effects of fixed effects and spatial. The significance of the test statistics for examining the fixed effects in Table 4 indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected and that both time-period and spatial fixed effects must be considered concurrently in the model's estimation.

The following table summarizes the estimation results for Eqs. (1) and (2) for the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial and the FMOLS model (5). The former is denoted by A, while the latter is denoted by B.

According to the results, the logarithm of GDP per capita's coefficient is positive and significant in all models, with coefficients ranging from 2.452 to 3.491. Thus, each percentage point increase in GDP results in an approximately 3% increase in CO2 emissions. Additionally, the negative and significant coefficient of GDP per capita squared on CO2 emissions varied between -0.067 and -0.147. As a result, the relationship between GDP growth and CO2 emissions is an inverted U-

Fig. 3. Shifting the EKC by ECI.

shaped relationship that supports the EKC hypothesis. Additionally, the significant coefficient of energy intensity at the 1% level indicates that energy intensity as a measure for energy efficiency results in increased CO2 emissions. Urbanization also increases CO2 emissions, but the effects are only significant when spatial and time-period fixed effects are used concurrently. The non-significant coefficients in the FMOLS model indicate that the variable has no long-term effect on CO2 emissions. Moreover, each percentage point increase in trade openness results in a positive and significant increase in CO2 emissions of 0.032%.

The economic complexity index indicates that models A1 and B1 have negligible effects on CO2 emissions. In a more detailed study, models A2 and B2 isolate the economic complexity index's spillover effects on energy efficiency improvement. Additionally, models A3 and B3 consider the ramifications of this for the relocation of the EKC. The following equations are derived from marginal effects of energy intensity on CO2 emissions calculated in models A3 and B3.

$$\frac{d(\ln CO_{2it})}{d(\ln ENER_{it})} = 0.96 - 0.193 \times ECI_{it} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d(\ln CO_{2it})}{d(\ln ENER_{it})} = 0.984 - 0.175 \times ECI_{it} \quad (6)$$

The relationships indicate that by increasing a country's economic complexity index, the boosting effects of energy intensity on increased CO2 emissions are mitigated, which means an improvement in energy efficiency. Furthermore, by substituting the coefficients into Eq. (3), the EKC is obtained as:

$$ED_{it} = (3.268 + 0.096 \times ECI_{it}) \times \ln GDP_{it} + (-0.135 - 0.006 \times ECI_{it}) \times \ln GDP_{it}^2 \quad (7)$$

$$ED_{it} = (3.491 + 0.062 \times ECI_{it}) \times \ln GDP_{it} + (-0.147 - 0.003 \times ECI_{it}) \times \ln GDP_{it}^2 \quad (8)$$

The EKC of Eq. (8) is shown in Fig. 3 for the maximum and minimum values of ECI (extracted from Table 2), highlighting the fact that ECI has shifted the EKC upward. The horizontal axis in the figure depicts the various logarithms of GDP per capita, while the vertical axis depicts the logarithm of corresponding CO2 emissions. The results demonstrated the economic complexity index's scale effects; that is, while increasing

energy efficiency improves the environment, increased economic growth spreads CO2 emissions and accelerates the process of environmental degradation. In models A1 and B1, the cumulative effect is not significantly different from zero.

Subsequently, to investigate long-term cointegration, Kao's cointegration test was performed on each set of variables and is included in the bottom section of the FMOLS model estimation tables. The significance of the test results confirms the existence of cointegration. Additionally, the Hausman test results determine whether the fixed effects model should be replaced with a random-effects model. The null hypothesis is rejected for all models, and fixed effects are confirmed at a 1% significance level.

Examining the estimation results of Eq. (4) without the interaction terms in Tables 5 and 6 reveals the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial and the FMOLS model produce approximately the same results (Table 7). While geothermal energy has decreased CO2 emissions, hydropower consumption has increased CO2 emissions and environmental degradation. Other coefficients associated with renewable energy components are irrelevant. The findings are consistent with the growing experimental literature, which indicates that consumption of renewable energies has not only failed to reduce CO2 emissions in some types of renewable energy but has increased them in others [22,25,27,28].

The interaction terms between the economic complexity index and various types of renewable energies have been included in Tables 8 and 9 to help understand how economic complexity contributes to this effect. Comparing the results of the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial and the FMOLS model reveals that the sign of the coefficients is nearly identical, except for some variables where the degree of significance of the coefficients varies. In both approaches, the coefficients of bioenergy and its term interaction are negligible. Additionally, for other types of renewable energy sources, the coefficients of interaction terms are positive. Furthermore, while the value of interaction terms is significant for all types of renewable energy (including wind, solar, hydropower, and geothermal energy resources) in the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial, the value of interaction terms is significant only for solar and wind energy sources in the FMOLS model. Hydropower energy once again exhibits a significant positive direct coefficient. Moreover, in the FMOLS model, only the direct coefficients of wind energy are positive and significant.

In general, the results indicate that the coefficients of interaction between wind and solar energy are positive and significant. The marginal effects of wind and solar energy on CO2 emissions are calculated concerning the FMOLS model coefficients:

$$\frac{d(\ln CO_{2it})}{d(\ln SOL_{it})} = 0.011 + 0.015 \times ECI_{it} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d(\ln CO_{2it})}{d(\ln WIN_{it})} = 0.95 + 0.162 \times ECI_{it} \quad (10)$$

Table 5The CO₂ model's estimation for Eqs. (1) and (2) using the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial and the FMOLS model.

	Spatial and time-period fixed effects			FMOLS		
	Model A1	Model A2	Model A3	Model B1	Model B2	Model B3
$\ln GDP_{it}$	2.694 (0.000***)	2.772 (0.000***)	3.268 (0.000***)	3.081 (0.000***)	3.142 (0.000***)	3.491 (0.000***)
$\ln GDP_{it}^2$	-0.100 (0.000***)	-0.105 (0.000***)	-0.135 (0.000***)	-0.121 (0.000***)	-0.125 (0.000***)	-0.147 (0.000***)
$\ln UR_{it}$	0.223 (0.020)	0.301 (0.001***)	0.092 (0.322)	0.144 (0.352)	0.212 (0.155)	0.057 (0.701)
$\ln OPE_{it}$	0.032 (0.000***)	0.033 (0.000***)	0.034 (0.000***)	0.036 (0.003***)	0.037 (0.002***)	0.038 (0.001***)
$\ln ENER_{it}$	1.018 (0.000***)	1.025 (0.000***)	0.960 (0.000***)	1.079 (0.000***)	1.083 (0.000***)	0.984 (0.000***)
ECl_{it}	0.020 (0.304)			0.013 (0.671)		
$\ln ENER_{it} \times ECl_{it}$		-0.024 (0.019**)	-0.193 (0.000***)		-0.023 (0.159)	-0.175 (0.000***)
$\ln GDP_{it} \times ECl_{it}$			0.096 (0.000***)			0.062 (-0.003***)
$\ln GDP_{it}^2 \times ECl_{it}$			-0.006 (0.000***)			-0.003 (0.293)
Log Likelihood	558.618	560.854	590.184			
R-squared	0.995	0.995	0.996	0.995	0.995	0.996
Hausman Test	84.556 (0.000***)	131.820 (0.000***)	271.743 (0.000***)			
Kao' test				-2.898 (0.002***)	-3.007 (0.001***)	-3.534 (0.000***)

Note: p-value, ***, **, and * show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations.

Positive values for interaction terms indicate that wind and solar energy generate more CO₂ emissions in countries with a higher economic complexity index, whereas negative values indicate the opposite. For hydropower and geothermal energy resources, the result can be accepted with less confidence.

Examining the data from the countries under study sheds light on the factors that contribute to this impact. The countries were classified as follows: 10 with a low economic complexity index, 10 with a medium economic complexity index, and 9 with a high economic complexity index. Between 2000 and 2018, renewable energy production increased by 122% in the first category, 133% in the second category, and 345% in the third category. This indicates that countries with a high economic complexity index have been instrumental in the global development of renewable energy resources. Additionally, Fig. 4 illustrates the percentage of renewable energy components used in each category from 2000 to 2018.

In countries with lower economic complexity indexes, the average share of hydropower energy production decreased from 99.83% in 2000 to 89.80% in 2018 (the average ECI was equal to -6.48 in 2000, -8.011 in 2018). Solar energy production accounted for less than 1% of total energy production in 2000 and increased to approximately 3.79% in 2018. Wind energy production increased from 0.02% in 2000 to 5.85% in 2018. Bioenergy's share of energy production increased from 0.15% to 0.56%, while geothermal energy remained constant at or near zero. As a result, solar and wind energy have partially displaced hydropower in countries with a lower economic complexity index. Since renewable energy production increased by only 122%, it has remained nearly constant.

The situation is quite different in countries with a higher economic complexity index. Hydropower's share has decreased significantly from

83.81% to 43.96%. Bioenergy and geothermal energy sources have also seen a decline in their share of the energy mix. Meanwhile, wind and solar energy have increased their share of the energy mix.

Thus, in more complex countries, in addition to a 3.45-fold increase in renewable energy production, there has been a significant shift away from older energy sources toward newer sources such as solar and wind. In other words, as technology advances and fossil fuels are replaced by solar and wind energy, other traditional methods of renewable energy production are being phased out.

4. Conclusion and policy implications

In this study, annual data for 29 Asia-Pacific countries over the period 2000–2018 were used to examine the effects of several determinant variables on CO₂ emissions, emphasizing the role of economic complexity. The conventional panel model with random and fixed effects was used to estimate the results, as was the fully modified OLS (FMOLS) model. Control variables such as trade openness, energy intensity, and urbanization significantly affect increasing CO₂ emissions, but these effects were not significant in long-term urbanization estimates. The EKC hypothesis was confirmed by the positive logarithm of GDP per capita and the negative coefficient of its squared form. The findings indicate that ignoring the environmental consequences of economic growth and trade openness can increase environmental pollution, implying that one of the primary economic management challenges is producing clean goods. According to the study results, economic complexity in countries results in an upward movement of the EKC, implying that as economic complexity in countries increases due to increased energy demand, scale effects occur, leading to increased CO₂ emissions. However, increasing energy efficiency is a side effect of

Table 6

The CO2 model's estimation for Eq. (4) without the interaction term using the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial.

	Model A4	Model A5	Model A6	Model A7	Model A8	Model A9
$\ln GDP_{it}$	2.597 (0.000***)	2.731 (0.000***)	2.644 (0.000***)	2.696 (0.000***)	2.629 (0.000***)	2.693 (0.000***)
$\ln GDP_{it}^2$	-0.095 (0.000***)	-0.102 (0.000***)	-0.096 (0.000***)	-0.100 (0.000***)	-0.095 (0.000***)	-0.100 (0.000***)
$\ln URB_{it}$	0.233 (0.010**)	0.249 (0.006***)	0.239 (0.009***)	0.262 (0.005***)	0.249 (0.006***)	0.238 (0.009***)
$\ln OPE_{it}$	0.028 (0.000***)	0.031 (0.000***)	0.032 (0.000***)	0.032 (0.000***)	0.033 (0.000***)	0.030 (0.000***)
$\ln ENER_{it}$	0.993 (0.000***)	1.026 (0.000***)	1.028 (0.000***)	1.023 (0.000***)	1.025 (0.000***)	1.013 (0.000***)
$\ln HYD_{it}$	0.069 (0.007***)					
$\ln SOL_{it}$		0.009 (0.520)				
$\ln WIN_{it}$			-0.031 (0.029**)			
$\ln BIO_{it}$				-0.035 (0.529)		
$\ln GEO_{it}$					-0.252 (0.003***)	
$\ln RENEW_{it}$						0.023 (0.221)
Log Likelihood	561.759	558.293	560.477	558.284	562.662	558.840
R-squared	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995
Hausman Test	71.279 (0.000***)	241.691 (0.000***)	62.209 (0.000***)	55.888 (0.000***)	183.119 (0.000***)	81.970 (0.000***)

Note: p-value, ***, **, and * show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 7

The CO2 model's estimation for Eq. (4) without the interaction term using the FMOLS model.

	Model B4	Model B5	Model B6	Model B7	Model B8	Model B9
$\ln GDP_{it}$	2.969 (0.000***)	2.769 (0.000***)	3.592 (0.000***)	2.790 (0.000***)	-12.424 (0.000***)	3.076 (0.000***)
$\ln GDP_{it}^2$	-0.116 (0.000***)	-0.103 (0.000***)	-0.153 (0.000***)	-0.107 (0.000***)	0.747 (0.000***)	-0.122 (0.000***)
$\ln URB_{it}$	0.153 (0.293)	0.255 (0.117)	0.344 (0.044**)	0.298 (0.138)	4.048 (0.000***)	0.143 (0.334)
$\ln OPE_{it}$	0.030 (0.011)	0.048 (0.000***)	-0.426 (0.000***)	0.044 (0.004***)	-2.580 (0.000***)	0.032 (0.008***)
$\ln ENER_{it}$	1.042 (0.000***)	1.079 (0.000***)	1.204 (0.000***)	1.023 (0.000***)	2.328 (0.000***)	1.064 (0.000***)
$\ln HYD_{it}$	0.079 (0.040**)					
$\ln SOL_{it}$		0.001 (0.957)				
$\ln WIN_{it}$			-0.016 (0.501)			
$\ln BIO_{it}$				0.006 (0.960)		
$\ln GEO_{it}$					-1.127 (0.000***)	
$\ln RENEW_{it}$						0.045 (0.122)
R-squared	0.995	0.995	0.991	0.996	0.858	0.995
Kao' test	-3.121 (0.001***)	-2.907 (0.002***)	-3.008 (0.001***)	-2.899 (0.002***)	-2.862 (0.002***)	-2.972 (0.002***)

Note: p-value, ***, **, and * show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 8
The CO2 model's estimation for Eq. (4) with the interaction term using the simultaneous fixed effects of time-period and spatial.

	Model A10	Model A11	Model A12	Model A13	Model A14	Model A15
$\ln GDP_{it}$	2.615 (0.000***)	2.950 (0.000***)	2.760 (0.000***)	2.694 (0.000***)	2.683 (0.000***)	2.764 (0.000***)
$\ln GDP_{it}^2$	-0.095 (0.000***)	-0.115 (0.000***)	-0.103 (0.000***)	-0.100 (0.000***)	-0.099 (0.000***)	-0.103 (0.000***)
$\ln URB_{it}$	0.190 (0.044**)	0.194 (0.031**)	0.216 (0.017**)	0.264 (0.004***)	0.255 (0.005***)	0.164 (0.085*)
$\ln OPE_{it}$	0.028 (0.000***)	0.027 (0.001***)	0.030 (0.000***)	0.032 (0.000***)	0.032 (0.000***)	0.030 (0.000***)
$\ln ENER_{it}$	0.994 (0.000***)	1.055 (0.000***)	1.035 (0.000***)	1.025 (0.000***)	1.022 (0.000***)	1.019 (0.000***)
$\ln HYD_{it}$	0.071 (0.005***)					
$\ln HYD_{it} \times ECI_{it}$	0.013 (0.090*)					
$\ln SOL_{it}$		0.006 (0.677)				
$\ln SOL_{it} \times ECI_{it}$		0.052 (0.000***)				
$\ln WIN_{it}$			0.012 (0.508)			
$\ln WIN_{it} \times ECI_{it}$			0.072 (0.001***)			
$\ln BIO_{it}$				-0.024 (0.708)		
$\ln BIO_{it} \times ECI_{it}$				-0.014 (0.715)		
$\ln GEO_{it}$					-0.033 (0.787)	
$\ln GEO_{it} \times ECI_{it}$					0.197 (0.014**)	
$\ln RENEW_{it}$						0.023 (0.225)
$\ln RENEW_{it} \times ECI_{it}$						0.018 (0.007**)
Log Likelihood	563.208	570.595	566.188	558.352	565.681	562.487
R-squared	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995
Hausman Test	121.916 (0.000***)	94.393 (0.000***)	58.504 (0.000***)	73.968 (0.000***)	132.966 (0.000***)	86.013 (0.000***)

Note: p-value, ***, **, and * show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.
Source: Authors' estimations.

economic complexity expansion, resulting in decreased energy intensity effects.

The specific results of this paper are to determine how renewable energy sources affect CO2 emissions. As the findings indicate, economic complexity is a critical factor in determining how renewable energy affects CO2 emissions.

In countries with a lower level of economic complexity, Solar and wind energies have increased their relative share of renewable energy production, while the total amount of renewable energy production has remained stable. Consequently, in the absence of scale effects associated with renewable energy consumption (since total renewable energy consumption has remained constant over the period under review), such a shift has had a beneficial effect on the environment. Under these circumstances, shifting from older forms of renewable energy to newer forms, like solar and wind, has reduced air pollution. Furthermore, the situation is different in high economically complex countries. Due to the spread of innovation and significant environmental challenges in countries with a higher level of economic complexity, two major changes have taken place: 1) The total amount of renewable energy produced has increased. Whereas the production process of renewable energies, like any commodity, is polluting, such a change leads to revealing the scale effects of renewable energy consumption and increasing CO2 emissions. 2) solar and wind energy share among various

types of renewable energy has increased. Hence, as new energy sources such as wind and solar are utilized more extensively, the intensity of the emission decreases. The experimental results indicate that the former enhancing effects are more significant than the latter declining effects on increasing CO2 emissions in countries with higher economic complexity. These findings, however, do not necessarily reflect the fundamental nature of renewable energies in the real world. Generating equivalent amounts of energy using fossil fuels results in significantly worse pollution, which experimental data cannot control and demonstrate.

Recommendations are made in light of the experimental findings. Concerning more complex countries, a focus on renewable energy production, process optimization, and structural changes in the industry can help prevent CO2 emissions [50]. When countries with low economic complexity lack the internal structure necessary to transition to renewable energy, attention should be directed toward energy supply and demand and industrial strategy development to reduce CO2 emissions and expand related innovations [51]. Additionally, environmental policies such as a carbon tax, green technologies investment, subsidies, and incentives for renewable energy infrastructure investment should be considered to expand renewable energy further.

Given that the economy has a different system goal (profit, growth) than the super system [52], it is necessary to consider the economy's orientation toward environmentally friendly technology. As a result of

Table 9
The CO2 model's estimation for Eq. (4) with the interaction term using the FMOLS model with the interaction term.

	Model B10	Model B11	Model B12	Model B13	Model B14	Model B15
$\ln GDP_{it}$	2.978 (0.000***)	3.081 (0.000***)	4.109 (0.000***)	2.805 (0.000***)	-11.723 (0.000***)	3.181 (0.000***)
$\ln GDP_{it}^2$	-0.115 (0.000***)	-0.120 (0.000***)	-0.186 (0.000***)	-0.107 (0.000***)	0.701 (0.000***)	-0.126 (0.000***)
$\ln URB_{it}$	0.114 (0.447)	0.150 (0.348)	0.301 (0.089)	0.281 (0.165)	4.151 (0.000***)	0.045 (0.766)
$\ln OPE_{it}$	0.030 (0.011)	0.041 (0.002***)	-0.483 (0.000***)	0.043 (0.005***)	-2.598 (0.000***)	0.030 (0.012)
$\ln ENER_{it}$	1.041 (0.000***)	1.121 (0.000***)	1.232 (0.000***)	1.017 (0.000***)	2.293 (0.000***)	1.074 (0.000***)
$\ln HYD_{it}$	0.083 (0.032**)					
$\ln HYD_{it} \times ECI_{it}$	0.012 (0.292)					
$\ln SOL_{it}$		0.011 (0.621)				
$\ln SOL_{it} \times ECI_{it}$		0.051 (0.007***)				
$\ln WIN_{it}$			0.095 (0.008***)			
$\ln WIN_{it} \times ECI_{it}$			0.162 (0.000***)			
$\ln BIO_{it}$				-0.042 (0.754)		
$\ln BIO_{it} \times ECI_{it}$				0.054 (0.446)		
$\ln GEO_{it}$					-0.641 (0.162)	
$\ln GEO_{it} \times ECI_{it}$					0.375 (0.181)	
$\ln RENEW_{it}$						0.046 (0.104)
$\ln RENEW_{it} \times ECI_{it}$						0.023 (0.027**)
R-squared	0.995	0.996	0.991	0.996	0.858	0.995
Kao' test	-3.125 (0.001***)	-3.402 (0.000***)	-3.176 (0.001***)	-2.893 (0.002***)	-2.905 (0.002***)	-3.105 (0.001***)

Note: p-value, ***, **, and * show significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.
Source: Authors' estimations.

Fig. 4. The average proportion of the renewable energy components.

the expansion of innovations and the development of economic complexity in countries, the use of technologies such as carbon capture and utilization (CCUS) and carbon capture and storage (CCS) must be expanded, as empirical studies have demonstrated their importance in reducing energy use intensity and their positive environmental consequences [53–55]. The Paris agreement aimed for a long-term global temperature increase of less than 1.5 °C. At the same time, such agreements are regulated independently of the countries' economic structures. Policymakers should consider the need for technological transfer of such innovations to countries with lower levels of complexity that lack internal mechanisms for their creation. Additionally, countries may consider promoting green lifestyles and raising public awareness about environmental degradation to be minimal measures. These measures can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions [56] and steer the economy toward increased investment in green industries via increased demand for green products.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohsen Khezri: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Almas Heshmati:** Formal analysis. **Mehdi Khodaei:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Resources, Software, Visualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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